

Towards a Theory of the Formal Situation: Developing a Minimal Unit of Sociological Analysis

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Abstract

The social sciences lack a foundational minimal unit of analysis that enables different theoretical perspectives to be compared on common ground. This paper addresses this gap by developing the concept of the Formal Situation as a universal descriptive model for social phenomena – drawing on various theoretical approaches, but primarily on Alfred Schütz's theory of the lifeworld.

The paper first examines how the concept of the situation is handled across major sociological theories, identifying recurring standpoints and perspectives. From this comparative analysis, a minimal set of dimensions necessary to describe any social situation is derived: space, time, and quantity as universal core dimensions, alongside exchange and impulse as operational principles. Central to the model is the Principle of the Tendency towards Unity – a generalizable motive, applicable to all situations and all living beings, according to which actors strive to preserve and expand their essential units. This principle builds upon Schütz's insight that the finiteness of human life constitutes the most fundamental motive for action, while extending it beyond the domain of human daily and life plans.

The situational base model is then related to language – which, following Schütz, represents the most fundamental form of human expression. It is argued that linguistic structures do not arbitrarily mirror reality but emerge as representations of formal situational dimensions, a claim subsequently developed in the analysis of Serial Verb Constructions (Bauer 2026).

Finally, the paper discusses how the principle of the formal impulse can provide a generalizable motive for any situation definition – one that functions pre-rationally, applies across theoretical traditions, and offers a basis for comparing sociological frameworks without privileging any single theoretical standpoint.

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1. Introduction

When it comes to sociological explanations, one sooner or later encounters the concept of the social situation. No social-scientific interpretation of society or of human beings can do without this concept. Yet the way this perspective is handled varies considerably across theoretical positions. An individual or group is always

related to a situation – one finds oneself inside or outside a specific situation. The transition from one situation to another is itself a situation. One cannot truly stand at the edge of a situation, except within a higher-order one. The boundaries of situations are unclear – when does a situation begin, and when does it end? When one is a stranger in a social gathering, one can feel deeply alone. This situation of exclusion exists within a higher-order situation that ostensibly promises interaction and communication.

Phenomenology approaches this phenomenon with caution. The situation is bounded by inner and outer horizons that are always open to further interpretation (cf. Husserl 1966:11); yet even the personal perspective – through the concept of the stream of consciousness – dissolves these boundaries again and causes them to blur (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:248). In everyday life, however, we are quite aware of situations delimited in terms of time, place, and theme. Situational forms appear along a continuum of meanings within theories – as an additive of perception in the form of horizons, or as boundary conditions in rational choice theory, all the way to the total situation in which even perception itself becomes part of the situation (cf. Merleau-Ponty 1966:91ff).

For Garfinkel, the situation encompasses all aspects of human coexistence – which is why he can state, in his breaching experiments, that there were no cases in which the situation could not be restored [PB: Engl. „restorable situation“; unfortunately rendered as „bereinigte Situation“ in the German edition] (Garfinkel 2020:93). This view presupposes the possibility of a snapshot of all dimensions of interaction, human perception, and cognition simultaneously. William I. Thomas, in his famous theorem on the definition of the situation, implicitly assumes that the problematic situation connects to a biographical situation – one might call it a narrative (cf. Thomas/Thomas 1928:572). When a situation fits into a narrative, it becomes comprehensible, real, and meaningful. Its meaning derives from the role the receiving narrative plays for future action.

Building on these reflections and various theoretical positions, this paper examines the conceptualization of the situation with reference to Schütz and other authors, with particular attention to how specific dimensions of the situation can be derived. Schütz also noted that objective and subjective standpoints in social-scientific research must be clearly distinguished, since many problems in sociological inquiry arise from the conflation of these perspectives. Prior to any investigation, a frame of reference should be chosen that is appropriate to the problem at hand and that determines the conceptual scope and limits of the research (cf. Schütz 1972:9). Part of the subsequent analysis will examine how the situation is connected to language – which Schütz identifies as the most important form of human expression. This is all the more significant given that sociological theories already employ complex concepts for describing actions and situations – such as disposition, interpretation, construction, action selection, and utility maximization – concepts that in turn rest on implicit or explicit assumptions about consciousness, will, self-concept, rationality, and legitimacy, in order to move actors from one situation to another. To account for this motivational and explanatory dimension, a generalizable formal impulse is

proposed. Overall, the hope is that social theories can be better understood and compared once we determine how these theories relate to the concept of the situation and what perspectives they adopt with regard to it. In the field of theoretical and methodological comparison, there are as yet few satisfactory approaches – to the point where one might be tempted to establish an independent research direction of „methodological comparison" (cf. Auras 2016:92).

2. Standpoints and Perspectives

A standpoint or perspective refers to the view of a situation, whereby the perspective depends on the position of the standpoint and changes more frequently than the standpoint itself. The paradox of conceiving oneself simultaneously as an object within the situation and as a viewpoint from which the situation is perceived was already emphasized by Merleau-Ponty (cf. 1966:91f). For him, the body is at once subject and object of the situation.

This ambiguity also resonates in Schütz. On the one hand, he describes the individual as a being who, in a relatively natural attitude toward the world, manages situations without questioning them. On the other hand, he also attributes to the individual the capacity for an exchange of standpoints (the general thesis of reciprocity), which is necessary for social action with fellow human beings (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:136f). This means that within a natural (subjective) attitude – one in which this reciprocity holds – a theoretical-reflexive attitude must already be conceivable.

Bourdieu, too, is aware of this paradox. He describes the "I" that grasps physical and social space while simultaneously being grasped by it. Only in a reflexive attitude can a person comprehend the world and gain knowledge (cf. Bourdieu 2013:167f). From an analytical standpoint, however, one must adopt a position – that is, choose an attitude for oneself and one's protagonists. The standpoint one adopts, for oneself or for the actors under consideration, can be localized or understood relationally as a position within a social order (cf. Bourdieu 2013:139). And from an observing or scientific perspective, it is necessary to occupy a position within a scientific framework – that is, at a particular level of abstraction.

Bourdieu argues on the one hand for a position – and thus a standpoint – in physical and social space (cf. Bourdieu 2013:167f); on the other hand, the individual can only grasp the world if it has already been grasped by the world. This reciprocal relationship is expressed in the standpoint of the habitus concept and in the perspectives of the dispositions. Bourdieu holds that habitus and dispositions replace standpoints and perspectives – a move directed against positions of methodological individualism and utilitarianism. In the present investigation, however, this concept is taken to introduce a new standpoint with possible perspectives: habitus becomes an analytical actor. What Bourdieu is unquestionably correct about is the coincidence of the unity of habitus with its associated dispositions and the given situation as a

possible sociological perspective (cf. Bourdieu 2013:178).

Garfinkel also has this unity of individual and situation in view, and in a certain sense goes even further than Bourdieu. He does not require analytical actors; his scientific observers descend to the level of the individual's reality and come to know the methods of situational management by placing themselves in opposition to ordinary practices. The shift in standpoint toward that of the analytical scientist occurs only in a second step, when the results of breaching experiments are evaluated – as in: "Common-sense knowledge of the facts of social life for members of society is institutionalized knowledge of the real world" (Garfinkel 2020:99).

Berger and Luckmann occupy an institutional standpoint from the outset, even as they repeatedly invoke the positions of individuals at the micro level as witnesses for their perspectives. The situation is determined by the objective reality of significant others (cf. Berger/Luckmann 1980:141). Objective or objectified reality is conceived as a total situation that must be secured. Berger and Luckmann speak of reality maintenance, which in the simplest case takes the form of conversation in boundary situations, but may also involve crisis management. The standpoint for such perspectives is therefore also inherently a moral one, covering the entirety of the relevant reality. This moral standpoint can be compared to a higher-order situation, which in neo-institutionalism corresponds to the cognitive institution (cf. Senge 2011:87). This totalizing view has already been suggested in Bourdieu and Garfinkel.

Talcott Parsons, in his voluntaristic theory of action, brought together norms and goals and for the first time defined four dimensions of action in his "unit act" (cf. Parsons 1949:43ff): actors, goals, situational conditions, and norms (values). Through the concept of role – which linked social norms and role expectations – structural-functionalist role theory developed on the basis of Parsons' framework. Its central elements are positions (structural locations in social relations) and functional roles, which connect positions to real incumbents. Notably, the individual is viewed in isolation from the situation. Goals (in effect, target situations) are achieved through the means available in the initial situation and through existing norms (values are translated into norms). This functionalist perspective takes the standpoint of the individual as its starting point and is extended, in systems-theoretical terms, to groups, organizations, and societies by shifting the standpoint to elements involving multiple actors. As can be seen in the AGIL schema developed later, however, the separation of individuals and situations is no longer sustainable. Where individual and situation are separate at the actor level, at the systems level the system itself becomes the situation, maintained and transformed through the functional interplay of sub-situations. Parsons nonetheless succeeds, for the first time, in consistently adopting different analytical standpoints within a single sociological model. In Max Weber, for instance, there is no model that in its totality covers both the micro-sociological and macro-sociological perspectives.

Whereas in systems theory the acting unit and the situation necessarily form a unity by design, individualist theories offer a range of approaches. In Blumer, the individual stands – perhaps still in the tradition of Parsons – in opposition to the situation. In his

first premise defining symbolic interactionism, the human being is confronted with objects that may in turn be natural things, human beings and their actions, groups, institutions, or orienting ideas. These objects constitute the situation (cf. Blumer 1969:2). To allow actors to participate in the situation, Blumer employs the principle of objectification. He draws on G.H. Mead's concept of role-taking, which requires a standpoint of the self from the outside and perceives the self as object. It remains unclear at what point the situation changes – already at the level of role-taking as imagination, or only upon acting in this sense. "Root images" in symbolic interactionism are perspectives from the standpoint of the researcher for analyzing the situation: "...root images represent the way in which symbolic interactionism views human society and conduct" (Blumer 1969:6). One can thus say that from the observer level (standpoint A), different perspectives are adopted at the actor level (standpoint B) in order to examine the meaning of the situation.

In Goffman, the situation becomes the primary subject for the first time. It is not seen, as in Schütz, through individual dimensions, but as a totality that must be maintained. He makes clear that the situation can be fundamentally influenced by those acting within it, depending on the audience – that is, the others present in the given situation. When one has the impression that mutual perspectives yield no further insight, one is backstage: the participants know one another. The frontstage is quite different; here one knows only one's fellow players. The knowledge gap between audience and actors can be exploited to define new situational perspectives based on expectations. To define the situation, one must influence the expectations of those involved. Goffman also provides the first indication of when a situation begins or ends: "I have said that when an individual appears before others his actions will influence the definition of the situation..." (Goffman 1959:6). He argues that it is important for individuals to use their appearance and their interpretation of others' reactions to define the situation in a way that remains stable for the forthcoming interaction. Those who open the situation are thus also those who sustain it. The situation endures as long as it is supported by the other actors. The standpoint is the actor level, though one might with some justification also take the situation itself – which is always controlled by someone – as the standpoint. How, then, can one find out what someone really thinks if they always present a different face in a situation? Goffman offers a clue here as well, based on the fact that actors communicate asymmetrically through intended expression and unintended impression. When unobserved, one does not control the impressions one gives off – such as facial expressions and gestures. With reference to an example, Goffman writes: "The Shetlander, in short, would observe the unobserved observer" (Goffman 1959:7). This means that in a reflexive, inner attitude, from observer standpoint C, one must observe a person (at standpoint B, in a reflexive, inner attitude) who is observing and evaluating an original person (at standpoint A) while not feeling observed. Whether the attitude of the original person at standpoint A is subjective or reflexive in perception, or expressed inwardly or outwardly (in a controlled manner), is irrelevant. What matters is that person B evaluates person A and conveys their unfiltered impression through facial expressions and gestures to a third party, who

can thereby see what person B actually thinks of person A. This Goffmanian example is important for the comparison of theories precisely because the evaluation of theories also involves at least three levels of situational reality: observer level 2 (C) – observer level 1 (B) – actor at the action level (A).

The subjective standpoint is, as noted above, also linked to a higher-order moral component. This component is present in all perspectives on the situation and influences the actions that arise from it. Sara Ahmed describes this higher-order situation as happiness, achievable through so-called happiness objects. She calls this form of intentionality "goal-oriented." When the object is attained, happiness does not automatically follow, since the object only points toward happiness. Happiness objects circulate in society and accumulate happiness conceptions as social goods. Happiness objects may be things, institutions, practices, or values (cf. Ahmed 2010). The definition of the supposed happiness situation can also turn negative when one's own happiness conceptions cannot be reconciled with the shared conceptions of others. In a vivid example, Sara Ahmed illustrates the compelling force of this higher-order situation: the case of a father and his queer daughter, in which the happiness object of family inverts into its opposite. The daughter is happy with her girlfriend and her life – until the father expresses his disapproval of this way of living. The happy daughter becomes unhappy, because she sees her father unhappy (cf. Ahmed 2010:42f). The daughter perceives herself not only as a unity with her girlfriend, but also as a unity with her father. The latter unity is now compromised, leading to mutual unhappiness. Here, worlds collide. In terms of formal unity, these are higher-order situations that must be preserved as essential units. This example illustrates the significance of the moral dimension of the actors' subjective standpoint. For Alfred Schütz, higher-order situations are realities that he connects to a distinct experiential and cognitive style (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:262). Realities are thus more closely linked to his concept of knowledge than to his concept of the situation. In Goffman, higher-order situations are comparable to primary frameworks, which are also described as interpretive schemata of the situation (cf. Goffman 1977:31). He distinguishes between social and natural frameworks, where only the social framework can be influenced by human beings. Blumer acknowledges values and norms as higher-order situational components, but treats them as secondary to the significance of social interaction: "A gratuitous acceptance of the concepts of norms, values, social rules, and the like should not blind the social scientist to the fact that any one of them is subtended by a process of social interaction [...]" (Blumer 1969:18f).

Rational choice theories attempt to provide both micro- and macro-sociological explanations; accordingly, the analytical standpoint scales at minimum across the number of persons under observation. Larger numbers of persons tend to form structures – referred to as groups, organizations, or societies. These are more difficult to analyze due to the lower frequency with which such systems occur and the generally greater challenges of observation. Rational choice theories therefore aim for deep explanation at the actor level. The actions of individual actors have consequences for phenomena at the macro level – as represented in the

macro-micro-macro model of James Coleman or Hartmut Esser (cf. Coleman 1990:6; Esser 1999:98f). Esser designates the transition from the macro to the micro level – that is, the assessment of the situation – as the "logic of the situation"; the actor level involving action selection as the "logic of selection"; and the transition to, or effects upon, the macro level as the "logic of aggregation" (cf. Esser 1999a:94ff). This reveals that the concept of situation only comes into play at the micro level – actors stand at a distance from the situation while remaining in interaction with it. The central analytical perspective in each case is the "logic" – that is, the set of rules for evaluating the situation, for selecting actions within the situation, or for aggregating the consequences of actions from the situation toward society. At the macro level, in contrast to the situation, there is the concept of the social system, which Esser describes somewhat vaguely as the "level of collective phenomena" (Esser 1999:97). The realities of the "logic of the situation" are designated by Esser, following Schütz, as "first-order constructs" of actors at the action level (cf. Esser 1999:94; "common-sense constructs" in Schütz 1964:248). Sociologists attempt to explain outcomes of action by assuming that actors behave in accordance with a particular model of action (MFS = model of frame selection). The MFS makes it possible to account for the influence of situational interpretation in the explanatory understanding of action (cf. Kroneberg 2011:120), thereby connecting the steps of situation definition and action selection. The totality of these three steps is designated as the sociologist's causal-analytical second-order construct (cf. Esser 1999:97f; Schütz 1964:248). This conceptual definition is significant insofar as it attempts to distinguish standpoints and perspectives at the action level from those at the observer level.

In the essay "The Social World and the Theory of Social Action," Alfred Schütz attempts to describe the conditions and possibilities of a scientific theory of action that not only meets objective scientific requirements but also places the subjective perspective of actors at its center. In this context, he criticizes social-scientific orientations – such as behaviorism, with its unverifiability of the other's intelligence – that believe they can bracket this perspective. Schütz in principle supports an objective frame of reference (standpoints and perspectives with regard to a topic), but insists that the social scientist should, prior to any investigation, choose a frame of reference appropriate to the problem at hand and one that determines the conceptual scope and limits of the inquiry. He observes that most errors in the social sciences arise from the conflation of objective and subjective standpoints (cf. Schütz 1972:9). Further: "For a theory of action, the subjective standpoint must be maintained with full rigor [...]. Securing this subjective standpoint is the only sufficient guarantee that the world of social reality will not be replaced by a fictitious, non-existent world constructed by the scientific observer" (Schütz 1972:9). "Objective standpoint" here refers to the observer level, and "subjective standpoint" to reality as experienced by actors. One's own personal standpoint toward situations at the actor level is not arbitrarily alterable, since it depends on the standpoints of others and on the standpoint of the generalized other. The personal standpoint, within the configuration of others' standpoints, becomes personal identity. G.H. Mead

speaks even of "character in the moral sense" when one internalizes the perspectives of the generalized other (cf. Mead 1993:205).

According to Schütz, at the actor level the individual is left only with the possibility of interpreting the situation. To speak of the construction of reality is to occupy a theoretical standpoint of the observer (cf. Figure 1). The actor can of course also become an observer and construct reality; in the lifeworld, however, in natural intuition, the actor only interprets. To construct means to form new concepts or conceptual contents of situations, situational sequences, and situational relations.

Figure 1: Levels of Abstraction

Social Situation	Personal Standpoint	Standpoints of Others	Standpoints of Generalized Others
Actor Level	Identity (Interpretation 1)	Social positions (Interpretation 2)	Institutions (Interpretation 3)
	Habitus (Disposition)		
Observer Level 1	Theoretical positions (Construction 1)	System domain (Construction 2)	Theory (Construction 3)
Observer Level 2	Differences between theories		

The prevailing view in the social sciences – with the exception of Garfinkel – that actors and observers remain on their respective levels does not hold. An actor can become an observer and develop their own concepts and methods regarding the situation. In such a case, observing researchers are already operating at observer level 2 and must clarify the differences between the actor's theory and their own theories with respect to the situation (see Figure 1). The number of observer levels is, moreover, open-ended; the description of theories and situations then proceeds via differentials of higher degrees. Once the relevant connections are understood, concept formation and theorizing at higher levels of abstraction should wherever possible be avoided, since empirical verification becomes more difficult as distance from the actor level increases and the number of intermediate steps grows.

At the actor level, there exists a continuum of perspectives for managing situations. Individualist theories allow actors to interpret situations from shifting standpoints and perspectives, while consolidating their own standpoint – their identity. In collectivist approaches, habitual actors confront situations with dispositional possibilities that can barely be influenced by the will. Durkheim speaks even of molds into which we must pour our actions (cf. Durkheim 2019:126). In rational choice theory, this continuum is also described as variable rationality, with reference to Max Weber's types of social action, which map this spectrum between the poles of purposively rational action and traditional action (cf. Kroneberg 2011:89; Weber 1984:44).

3. Dimensions of the Formal Situation

Is there a minimal set of parameters sufficient to describe the social situation unambiguously? In Parsons, we saw that the situation is determined by specific elements such as actors, situational conditions, norms, and values. Blumer confronts his individual in the situation with objects that – alongside natural things – may include actors, groups, orienting ideas, and the individual itself. It appears that there are at least two categories of situational dimensions: those that the perceiving individual adds to the situation, and those of objective situational elements that an observer can also identify. One can further say that of the general situation to which the individual is exposed, usually only a part or section is relevant. This perspective – the framing of the situation, or in symbolic interactionism the attribution of meaning – depends on the constellation of situational elements and influences situational expectation.

For Hartmut Esser, situational elements consist, alongside actors, of the actors' constructs or bridge hypotheses (cf. Esser 1999:94). Esser identifies two fundamental motives of human action that co-determine the definition of the situation: physical well-being and social esteem. Both goals are necessary for the successful reproduction of the organism, and situations and actions are subsumed, together with these goals, under a concept of utility. Social intermediate goals or primary intermediate goods – such as status or money – arise in relation to these fundamental motives but differ between and within societies. They constitute the dominant goals of actors, also called "preferences" (cf. production functions in Esser 2004:115ff). Framing combines a focus on a superordinate goal (target situation) with the selection of the "right" model for the given situation (cf. Esser 2004:128f). Esser also draws on the concept of attitude used by Schütz (cf. Schütz 2003:136, 238, 256f). In a closed meaning-world, familiar interpretive schemata and relevance structures are drawn upon; or, when experiential knowledge is insufficient to manage the situation, a deliberate search for an interpretive solution is undertaken. In Esser's terminology, we are then in the domain of the as-mode and the rc-mode. Action selection can thus proceed in an automatic-spontaneous manner (as-mode) or consciously in a reflexive-calculative mode (rc-mode). This brief examination shows that situational elements in Esser's social theory serve only as preliminary steps or selections toward the action decision. For Esser, the process is explicitly one of situational reconstruction. Explanation proceeds via empirically accessible results; the actor does not know at the outset where the process will lead (cf. Esser 1999:104). For this reason, no immanent prognostic possibilities can be assumed for sociological explanation in Esser's sense, since the subjective meaning of actors is not at the center of the investigation. Subjective meaning is attributed to actors retrospectively in the course of research. A prognosis could, however, be made by the observing scientist if the respective as- and rc-modes of the actors and their situational definitions were known. Esser has thus introduced, as just shown, two distinct knowledge elements that can be described as higher-order situations: on the one hand, framing as the immediate bracket of a current situational domain; and on

the other, the fundamental motives of human action as a far broader frame of the current situation.

Alfred Schütz examined the dimension of knowledge more closely and investigated situational conditions in connection with the acquisition of knowledge. For him, at every moment of conscious life one finds oneself in a situation. The situation is on the one hand open through one's own biography and one's own experiences (knowledge), since it can be defined in different ways. On the other hand, it is bounded by world-time, inner duration, and the body (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:150f). The world is divided into an attainable and restorable zone of operation, which differs from the world within potential reach (cf. Figure 2).

Experience also has a social dimension. Situations differ according to the degree of possibility of interchangeability with others. Schütz speaks here of mediate and immediate relationships, graded according to degrees of anonymity (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:102ff, 154). In this connection, one might postulate a dimension of exchange or of communication and interaction with others. A further dimension appears to be concealed within the social dimension in Schütz, though he does not emphasize it. This is the number of actual and possible partners in cooperation – or more generally, the number of objects in the situation. This dimension of quantity is important for the individual's experience and situational assessment, because it conceals the quality of the power of the reciprocal relationship. Bourdieu expressed this connection as position in social space. Ultimately, it is decisive whether one as an individual stands opposite many, whether one stands opposite groups or institutions, or whether one as an individual is even a representative of an institution.

Figure 2: Structures of the Lifeworld (after Schütz/Luckmann 2003)

Other Worlds (forms of consciousness)	Life World	Time dimension	State of consciousness	Knowledge	Relevance system	Social structure	Premises
dream world fantasy world sleep (transc.)	future (transcendental)	world time	notions / ideas reality accent	typings	thematic relevance	Condition for subj. relevance and knowledge acquisition	(1) people with similar mindset
	posteriority	generations biographical articulation					
s p a c e d i m e n s i o n	world within reach	present	"first things first" (motives for action)	experiences	interpretive schemes explanatory schemes horizons	social imprint	as me
	society	Situation					
	institutions	eff. zone/act. range	consciousness I / self body	Pretention subj. duration Retention	tension of consciousness	interpretive relevance	
	contemporaries	fellow men (you) contemporaries (we)	(again and again,			and so forth)	general thesis: Interchangeability of points of view and congruence of systems of relevance
objects				language			
history (transcendental)		past with personal experience	curriculum vitae	sedimentation	motivational relevance		
		prehistoric world					

This also allows for a theory-related scaling from the micro level through the meso level to the macro level. The last dimension mentioned by Schütz is the motive or impulse. A situation is in a sense meaningless – or indeed not a situation at all – if the motive with which actors confront that situation is omitted. Without a motive, there is no subsequent situation, even if the situation changes objectively through the time dimension. The situation would not be distinguishable as a situation. In Schütz, motives are articulated through daily and life plans according to different degrees of urgency (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:172).

A situation is therefore a unity of objects – or more formally, a unity of units. From this, the following dimensions for describing a formal social situation can be derived:

(1) Time: world-time, inner subjective duration, biographical perspective. **(2) Space:** the spatial world of our perception and imagination. **(3) Quantity:** the number of actors, groups, or institutions; but also non-impulse-capable objects such as things or possessions, or frequencies such as the number of agreements per unit of time. **(4) Impulse:** according to Schütz, these are prioritized daily or life plans; in rational choice theory, preferences or primary intermediate goods; but at a more fundamental level, a concept of a basic impulse can also be described – see the chapter on "Situation Definition." **(5) Knowledge:** this encompasses experiences, knowledge of the world and of our body, consciousness, natural objects, possessions, and biography. The knowledge dimension is self-referential, since elements of knowledge can themselves constitute situations – including higher-order situations. Knowledge is distinguished at minimum into typical knowledge and detailed knowledge. **(6) Exchange:** this dimension concerns the fact that in a social situation one must have the possibility of standing in an exchange relationship with others and of being able to alter the situation through this reciprocal interaction. Exchange also encompasses perception and effect, and finds concrete expression in the concepts of communication, interaction, and action. Society itself is primarily an exchange situation, if one follows Roberto Esposito's (1998) etymological account of the concept of community: the term carries an ambiguity. While *communis* means "common," the less frequently used *cum munus* – "with an obligation/gift" – is associated with the duty to give and receive. The idea of a debt that one owes to other members of a group is the foundational principle of a community and secures close relations among members of the same group. Georg Simmel sees in exchange the objectification of value (cf. Simmel 1900:55). In the reciprocal interaction of exchange, the situation can be represented through a value. Exchange is also sexuality in the sense of bonding and reproduction.

Initially, I considered whether value might constitute a distinct situational dimension of its own, since every situation is evaluated in some form. Value is understood here as a generic concept – the situation can be assessed both in terms of a means-end relation and through its embedding in a higher-order (moral) situation. The value of a situation might generally be defined as follows: every situation receives a place within a receiving situation. Because that place is not arbitrary, it carries a value

within an order (cf. the German *Stellenwert*, meaning "place value" or "significance"). Situational evaluation stands, in the form of situational definition, at the very center of many sociological theoretical approaches. However, relevances, meanings, and power can be traced back to the relationship among the configurations of the dimensions listed above. Situational evaluation is therefore not a dimension in its own right, since its irreducibility cannot be guaranteed. The concept of value is merely a perspective or construction based on the constellation of situational dimensions – but it is of essential practical and analytical significance as a single reference point for assessing the situation.

A dimension in isolation carries no meaning; meaning arises only through the interaction of the individual situational elements. A situation changes only when its thematic relevance changes (cf. Schütz 2003:258f, 263f). While a situation can change at any moment – which would also define the smallest possible duration of a social situation – people make considerable efforts to maintain a desirable situation. They converse, they act virtuously, or they at least conform to norms and laws. Changes in situation generally proceed in a regulated and routine manner, even when these implicit methods and background expectations are not consciously available to individuals (cf. Garfinkel 2020:79). Situations that change in this way do not alter higher-order situations, or do so only slowly. The dimension of quantity is significant here: as long as the majority of those involved sustain the situation, it can be maintained. The economic situation of a country remains stable as long as most enterprises function as usual. A boundary situation is one that threatens the stability of a higher-order situation – such as crises, natural disasters, or death (cf. Berger/Luckmann 2016:167). Here one also sees again the aspect of the self-referentiality of the situation: not only does knowledge build on situations and situational sequences (actions), but the actors of situations can themselves be situations.

All social situations have active configurations of the spatio-temporal dimension and the dimension of quantity. Generic situations such as symbols, objects, or materials have no active configuration of the exchange and impulse dimensions. These are activated only when employed by actors. In real social situations there is in any case more than one unit of the quantity dimension. Each unit is, from a micro-social perspective, conceived as an actor and possesses an impulse, a share of personal and shared knowledge, and active exchange relationships. In imagined situations, the dimensions of impulse, exchange, and knowledge of other units within the situation are controlled by the individual.

4. Situation, Social Action, and Language

Through the exchange dimension, situational sequences are defined within the situation. Situational sequences are a succession of situational changes within a situation. They can lead to a change in the social situation. Every action can therefore be conceived as a process of successive situational changes and as an element of knowledge. A social action is accordingly present when individuals standing in exchange relations pursue imagined target situations. The orientation toward the goal of action is designated as meaning. This requires at minimum one action impulse on the part of a participant. Schütz sees this in a similar way. Actions are motivated sequences of experience, whereby the driving motive of the action is the attainment of a goal (target situation). Experiences are thematically marked lived events (situational contents) that are projected as drafts into the future (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:450f). The essential cognitive achievement thus concerns the draft. Behavior is action from the observer's perspective, whereby actors are always simultaneously acting and observing (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:454). For Schütz, meaning is a reference point established in consciousness between experiences and current situations or goals (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:449); at the actor level, this can only be subjective meaning, since the respective experiences are in principle inaccessible to outsiders. The objective meaning of action is expressed in meaning-adequate concepts and categories of language (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:452).

In Goffman, too, situation, action, and language are closely connected. Every action or performance takes place in a situation characterized by the props and facade of the actors (cf. Goffman 1959:22). Interaction is controlled through two channels of communication. Through language – as an objective representation of situations – action can be deliberately influenced. The impression given off, such as facial expressions, gestures, or manner of speaking, is by contrast not fully subject to conscious control. Yet it completes the information available to the actors involved, enabling them to better assess the intentions behind the action (cf. Goffman 1959:2). With the communicative forms of exchange and deception, central theoretical elements of Goffman are connected to the exchange dimension.

Whereas in Schütz language describes the situation – and through the relationship between situations also meaning – in Garfinkel language serves to maintain the situation. Language is thus an objectification of situations but also itself a situation. This perspective had already been realized in the philosophy of language, which linked language to speech acts – that is, to actions. Actions, however, as already noted, are elements of knowledge that can themselves be conceived as situations (self-referentiality). Language might also be described as a manifestation of the formal situation. It is precisely this perspective that Jürgen Habermas made productive for sociology.

In Habermas, speaking itself becomes action or the coordination of action, also because he conceives of language as a kind of mirror of situations. "With the concept of communicative action, the presupposition of the linguistic medium comes

into play, in which the actor's world-relations as such are reflected" (Habermas 1995:141). In essence, the three world-relations – the objective world, the social world, and the subjective world – correspond to the dimensions of knowledge, exchange, and impulse. With the qualification that Habermas removes his actor from the situation and assigns to him relations to the dimensions, which are in turn evaluated according to formal-logical and ethical criteria. Formal-logical (true) and ethical (truthful/sincere) perspectives are deliberately excluded from the model of the formal situation in order to establish a basis for theoretical comparisons – although they are implicitly reintroduced through the consideration of the "world of language." The subjectivity of the social scientist is precisely the emphasis on perspective. Discourse consensus would have to function as agreement on shared target situations. In contrast to communicative action, strategic action is concerned with the compatibility of achieving different target situations.

Without going into the process of knowledge acquisition in detail, one can nonetheless say that, when successful, it leads to a modified or new concept or to a new conceptual connection. Perspectives and/or standpoints regarding the situation, or derived concepts, have changed. The dimensions of language can also be conceived as dimensions of the situation – whereby the situation actually precedes language and holds more states than can sometimes be expressed through language. Yet the unspeakable is quickly captured in concepts through the combination of standpoints and perspectives on the situation in question. For Schütz, signs are "objectifications of subjective knowledge." Sign systems enable the transmission of subjective knowledge independent of the situation in which it was acquired (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:377). Signs and concepts are therefore perspectives on situations. In the course of objectification, a detachment from the original acquisition situation occurs; the concept then refers to a typical formal situation, while the original situation can still be recalled. The mediation situation (we-relationship) of a sign or concept creates the basis for connecting a concept with a situation for different people. Schütz formulates this as follows: "Under these conditions [shared signs in a mediation situation], subjective knowledge can be translated into the 'idealizing' and 'anonymous' matrices of meaning of the sign system [...]" (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:380).

Language, however, is in a certain sense always something more than the immediate situation it describes. Concepts are embedded in sentences and narratives that represent higher-order situational connections or realities. Narratives also have the capacity to detach themselves from real situations and to link imagined situations. But they can become real when a sensorially perceived situation fits seamlessly into such a narrative. This constellation describes the Thomas theorem. The decisive point, however, is the insertion of a situation or situational connection into an existing narrative of our knowledge that is important to us – this process constitutes understanding. The time dimension is dominant in narrative. The sequence of situations, as well as the outcome of an action, can thus be interpreted causally. Nevertheless, subjective understanding initially carries no causal meaning; rather, it is perceived as a unity – "true" also in the sense of preserving (German

bewahren). This tendency towards unity will be elaborated further in connection with the dimension of impulse.

Products as the outcomes of an action are objectified target situations. For Schütz these can be markers, tools, or works of art. They are in principle accessible to us through concepts. Using the example of the tool, Schütz explains the concept of "interpretation": "The interpretation of a tool refers essentially to its function in an in-order-to connection [...], whereby the specific maker can in principle remain anonymous" (Schütz/Luckmann 2003:373). In other words: a situation or situational content can become significant for the attainment of a projected goal. The process therefore describes only future understanding. The situation receives a place in a forward-directed narrative. A situation thus has meaning when one (or others) can retrospectively bring understanding to the inclusion of that situation. It was meaningful for someone to eat an ice cream on a warm summer day. Others were retrospectively able to understand this action. Subsequent rationalization attempts to embed the situation in the overall narrative of the person in question, in order to avoid contradictions: "Although I am on a diet, I can allow myself an ice cream because I exercise."

In a certain sense, the dimensions of the situation are reflected in language. This is apparent in the W-questions (who, what, where, when, why, how), which seek to clarify dimensional or situational relations. Or in sentence structures that relate individual dimensional concretizations to one another (impulse–exchange–knowledge vs. subject–predicate–object). Sentence configurations such as active and passive voice describe different standpoints and perspectives. With the subjunctive, situations and situational connections are varied. The existence of grammatical gender in language has no dimensional basis. The use of gender-related attributions is determined through the typicality of knowledge and the exchange relation.

Excursus on linguistic gender practice: The explicit naming of all genders in concepts is only partially suitable for describing neutral actors, since the explicit incorporation of gender type into concept formation produces an emphasis on a particular type and therefore already reinforces a perspective. To correctly describe neutral actors, grammatical gender would accordingly have to be removed from the concepts.

/Excursus

A concept is a perspective on a situation. All concepts can be traced back to situations. This will be illustrated by the examples of "role" and "disposition." The concept of role is a perspective on the situation from the observer's standpoint. It attributes typical knowledge (status or position) to specific actors in the given situation. From this shared knowledge – which is only a subset of the respective actors' knowledge – possible exchange relations and target situations arise. In Parsons' sense, the shared socially acquired knowledge (role-taking) is sufficient to manage the situation. The emphasis falls more heavily on the knowledge dimension. In symbolic interactionism, by contrast, shared knowledge is less clearly defined and situational expectations differ. Depending on one's perspective, this creates either latitude or conflict potential, leading to reflexive negotiation processes and

interpretive situational readings (role-making). The focus of the role perspective lies on the exchange dimension.

Whereas the concept of role is also used in the lifeworld description of situations at the actor level, the concept of disposition has remained at the observer level. With dispositions, there is a considerably larger shared domain of knowledge among actors – Bourdieu calls it habitus. It encompasses not only experiences relating to the current situation but also higher-order situations (shared narratives) that apply in similar measure to all actors and must be maintained through corresponding actions in the current situation. Within this general knowledge framework there are specific features attributed only to certain actors. These actors occupy, through their attributed typical knowledge, positions in social space. This shared knowledge of position-holders determines the dispositions – that is, the exchange relations of those involved. These are given for each situational constellation and correspond to the mostly unconscious background expectations of shared experience and to shared attitudes toward the situation. Bourdieu also states clearly that positions align themselves with the superordinate habitus, and not the other way around (cf. Bourdieu 2013:202). The knowledge dimension thereby becomes the central perspective in relation to the given situation. Exchange and impulse are in many cases secondary and can do little to alter the reproduction of knowledge contents. This means that knowledge is reproduced by calling up practices (elements of the knowledge dimension) in confrontation with a situation. Dispositional actions can be concretized in fitting situations and, in this conceptual framework, also describe the behavior of habitual actors such as groups or institutions (variation of the quantity dimension). The concept of disposition is therefore a particular perspective on situations and situational relations, one that can be described by means of the formal situation.

5. The Definition of the Situation

Not all situational elements are equally significant. Often only a section of the situation is relevant. An example would be the walk of a geologist and a botanist. The geologist notices particular stones along the path; the botanist perhaps flowers by the wayside. Each of these situational sections is embedded in a higher-order situation within the lifeworld of the respective actors. Subsequent situations are therefore dependent on the assessment and interpretation of the current situation. In structural functionalism, constraints on action and goals are described through constructive knowledge elements such as roles, norms, or values. Norms are situations in which typical actions lead to typical subsequent situations. Norms are available as shared knowledge. One usually also knows the typical situations that arise in cases of deviant behavior. One's own deviant behavior simultaneously triggers typical behavior in others (sanctions), which can be defined through the exchange dimension. Internalization describes, in a certain sense, the process by

which a lived norm is elevated to a value (value genesis) and one's own deviant behavior is sanctioned. Values are thus also higher-order situational goals that become anchored in the knowledge of the individual through processes of learning and reflection. Parsons describes this relationship between value and norm in reverse order, whereby actors in specific situations derive norms from values, "because values are relatively abstract" (Kroneberg 2011:64). In this reversed perspective (the effect of values), one sees that values operate through norms as situational connections – but only when we regard these values as relevant in the situation. Another form of higher-order situation is the institution, which arises from the normed and objectified actions of many. The institution can be conceived not only as a situation but, through the quantity dimension, also as an actor of actors, since it is capable of generating impulses. Values or institutions influence the situational situation as knowledge when they are relevant to the situation. Schütz designates motivational relevance (or in our terminology, impulse relevance) as the most important relevance structure, from which he derives thematic relevance (which situational elements are important) and interpretive relevance (which situational details are unclear and require clarification) (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:282). The following example may serve as illustration: if one lives according to ecological values, this value determines various actions such as shopping, eating, living, or traveling. If one finds oneself in a situation of illness, another knowledge unit such as the body may gain in relevance. An unecological flight to the seaside for therapeutic reasons is now accepted, because another knowledge unit – health – gains in relevance. One can therefore say that while the definition of the situation is influenced by all situational dimensions, the impulse dimension plays a particularly important role. It determines the relevance of a knowledge element with respect to a situation. In the example given, it is the impulse to preserve an essential unit.

In the interpretive paradigm, the interactive process of "mutual indication and interpretation" (Kroneberg 2011:70) as well as the actors' situational attribution of meaning (cf. Reckwitz 2004:314) are regarded as the definition of the situation. In this process, meaning is attributed to only a part of the situation. Goffman designated this concept as framing (cf. Goffman 1977:35f), which depending on one's perspective can also be described as focus formation, selection, or a process of inclusion and exclusion of knowledge. Although the focus of situation definition in the negotiation process thus appears to lie in the exchange dimension and in the knowledge brought to or shared in the situation, the impulse nonetheless plays a decisive role in determining which situational elements become significant. It is undisputed, however, that the current impulse can change in the course of the situation. This also implies that one must assume the existence of higher-order and current impulses. Alfred Schütz uses the term plan hierarchies for this, within which current interests are embedded (cf. Schütz/Luckmann 2003:172).

Howard S. Becker describes a situation in his essay "Becoming a Marijuana User" using methods of symbolic interactionism. In order to derive pleasure from smoking marijuana, one must discover the practices that lead to this through an interpretive process. Although many subjects initially fail to achieve the goal of getting "high" –

and on the contrary have negative experiences – they make repeated attempts. Becker does not conceal the fact that a learning process is involved in using the drug correctly in order to get high and enjoy its effects. "Enjoyment is introduced by the favorable definition of the experience that one acquires from others" (Becker 1953:241). This means, however, that one must discover the best experience in order to reach the goal by comparatively evaluating outcomes (because-motives in Schütz). Renewed attempts can be described with in-order-to motives. The motive is thus clearly given from the outset: one wants to become a marijuana user, with the immediate goal of the positive experience of "highness." In the formal situation, this motive is designated as an expansion impulse – the initiated action expands a knowledge unit that is essential to the actor. Expansion impulses in attitude and expectation toward the situation are always connected with wishes, dreams, or desires for the preservation or expansion of a knowledge unit. In the case of successful expansion, one feels joy. What is missing in Howard S. Becker's study? It is the description of the situation from the perspective of the impulse dimension. What is the essential knowledge unit that the actors wish to expand? If it is merely the expansion of an ability that one has come to know through comparison with others, then it is indeed an expansion impulse. But it may also be the case that one no longer belongs to the group in a certain sense if one does not master this ability. In that case, this expansion impulse is preceded by a preservation impulse, signaling the loss or impairment of a unit. This also means that a comprehensive definition of the situation is only present when all situational dimensions are brought to the center of the analysis from their respective perspectives.

The development of actions is described, depending on the sociological theoretical orientation, through disposition, interpretation and construction, or action selection and utility maximization – with explicit and tacit presuppositions such as consciousness, will, self-concept, rationality and judgment, or legitimacy.

A formal definition of the impulse naturally cannot work with already elaborated theoretical concepts. It should also function pre-rationally, and it must provide a generalizable motive. Nevertheless, emotionality is presupposed in human actors, and a certain rationality is presupposed in all actors. The formal impulse is based on the thesis of the principle of the tendency towards unity. This principle has two states – the preservation and the expansion of a knowledge unit, whereby preservation takes priority. The tendency towards unity also influences the exchange dimension with an open balance of expectations. These attitudes are described with concepts such as wishes, dreams, striving, or desire for the preservation or expansion of a knowledge unit. "All human beings by nature desire knowledge" (Aristotle 1970:16). The actual impulse describes a situation between perception and effect.

The following conditions are required to describe a formal impulse: (1) Essential knowledge units: these are in essence knowledge units that are close to us (body, family, certain values). They describe the nature of the actor unit. (2) Principled relevance of knowledge units or situations: this is described through temporal and spatial proximity to the current situation. Tomorrow's appointment is more relevant than one a year from now; the queue at the restroom more relevant than one at the

zoo. (3) Knowledge elements exhibit situationally typical characteristics: typically, a hot stove is good for cooking but dangerous if one places one's hand on it. (4) Knowledge elements have a situational exchange value: not to be confused with a general or moral value, which can also be a goal.

With every impulse, a relationship between essential knowledge units and the perceived situation is established through perception – that is, a unity is formed. The unity may fit or it may not. If it does not fit, an essential knowledge unit may be in danger or lost; one experiences emotions from the preservation spectrum (defensive feelings, feelings of loss) and, alongside the immediate emotional responses, initiates actions to preserve the relevant unit. If the new knowledge element fits as an expansion of the relevant unit, one experiences emotions from the expansion spectrum (feelings of happiness) such as joy or satisfaction. A particular form of knowledge expansion is confrontation with the situation in the sense of proximity or exposure. Although the unity originally does not fit, after prolonged proximity it is internalized. This form of knowledge acquisition occurs above all in situations of primary socialization. An impulse toward preservation or expansion can also set in motion the development of planned or imagined situations (in Schütz, daily or life plans). Preservation impulses also generate, in the exchange relation, needs (and values) for maintaining our bodily integrity. We therefore engage in activities, pursue a profession, and attempt through the exchange dimension, according to the principle of supply and demand, to obtain the knowledge elements of daily need. In this way, the concept of supply and demand – as indeed causality itself – can be traced back to the principle of the tendency towards unity.

An important measure for maintaining the unity of the situation is usually described through the perspective of tolerance. Tolerance defines the difference in a conception of unity in comparison with other actors. A change in situation can trigger a preservation impulse in one actor but not (yet) in another.

The preservation or expansion of the current essential unit in the course of a situation definition also touches upon higher-order units defined through the knowledge dimension. These too must be preserved or expanded when they are important to us; otherwise dissonances threaten. There are only finitely many higher-order situations and one highest, irreducible moral situational unit, which we acquire in primary socialization through the exchange dimension with others and cannot simply change. Berger and Luckmann describe the dependence of the impulse on higher-order situations as the alignment of action with plausibility structures (cf. Berger/Luckmann 2016:165f).

When one wishes to analyze a social phenomenon, it is therefore advisable to first identify the essential knowledge units affected. Why, in the COVID-19 pandemic, was there a divide between vaccine proponents and vaccine opponents? Vaccine proponents presumably perceive their body, their health, or their social integrity (the higher-order situation of profession or group) as threatened. Vaccination serves to preserve these essential units. The impulse can be embedded in a scientific explanatory system, which in isolated cases may even be regarded as an absolute moral unit. In any case, the community of vaccine proponents forms a higher-order

situation that, on account of its quantity, can be described as a norm situation and thereby also excludes dissonances regarding the vaccination issue [Note: every situation can of course contain sub-situations, whereby the higher-order situation also applies to these]. For vaccine opponents, by contrast, vaccination becomes a threat to units that are important to them. At least three types can be distinguished. First, those who do see their body and health as threatened, but prefer natural methods for preserving these units and regard vaccination as a more probable threat than infection. This natural path can stand for different worldviews. Second, those inclined toward conspiracy theories, who see the coronavirus as a false-flag operation by a group – accordingly, the threat to health and higher-order units emanates from this group. Here, however, the situational interpretation also gives rise to an expansion impulse for one's own conspiracy narrative, which becomes situationally determining as an essential unit. A third type does perceive a fundamental threat to their own health but regards the expansion potential of their own political group as a more important situational unit, by supporting vaccine opponents. Vaccine opponents are from this perspective a heterogeneous group, moving along a continuum between the preservation and expansion of their units.

At its core, this differing perception – which leads to the attitudes described – is self-evident for each group. The respective essential unit – in Thomas S. Kuhn's terms, the paradigm – forms a unity with the perceived matter of vaccination, which is apprehended as true. Kuhn himself describes how the worldview changes through a paradigm shift: "Looking at a contour map, the student sees lines on paper, the cartographer a picture of a terrain" (Kuhn 1976:123). The paradigm in Kuhn's sense is thus a prime example of a higher-order situation that is seen as a unity and that is preserved and expanded by those who believe in it.

An impulse thus motivates actions and goals. But it also defines the situation by increasing or decreasing the relevance of certain knowledge elements within it. At the same time, in the exchange relation with other actors in the situation, the exchange value of knowledge elements is established. If one regards consciousness as a knowledge element in which all relevant elements of the situation come to presentation, this does not apply to all situations and actions. In the habitual practices and everyday actions described by Bourdieu or Garfinkel, this tendency towards unity is enacted without rational reflection.

6. Conclusion

If one wishes to compare sociological theories, one must be able to situate their central building blocks. The situation is the conception to which every theoretical domain can be traced back. This undertaking can be realized through a comparison of the respective standpoints and perspectives on situations and through the representation of their differences. Moreover, every theory is mediated to us through language. For this reason, the description of language and situation is of

fundamental importance for understanding the relationship between these categories. Finally, a formal description of the situation can only succeed if the number of situational dimensions is reduced to a minimum in the spirit of Occam's razor. It can indeed be debated whether the impulse constitutes a dimension or a foundational principle.

The model of the formal situation presented here also represents an attempt to counteract the opposition between individual and society that Norbert Elias rightly lamented (cf. Elias 1993:132). Through the exchange dimension, the situation already contains the dynamics of figuration. Rather than directing the perspective toward the entanglement of objects, the potentiality of the entanglement of the object is foregrounded. The situation is thus already entanglement.

Given the length constraints of this text format, several areas have only been sketched. The following topics therefore await more thorough treatment: emotions are essential for the description of the formal impulse – a genealogy of emotions would accordingly be a natural subject of investigation. A deeper examination of the relationship between language and situation would be desirable, as would a more detailed structural clarification of the knowledge dimension. Although the perspectives of many sociological research fields – such as the sociology of culture, conflict sociology, or the sociology of science – can be represented through the concept of this situational model, a more in-depth analysis would be needed to clarify their integration. Whether one can in fact dispense with psychological instances such as the ego or the will within the impulse dimension, and derive all social phenomena from the formal definition of the situation, remains to be demonstrated. Nor have I addressed a systematic comparison of the concept of artificial intelligence with the model of the formal situation.

Finally, a remark on the state of theory in the social sciences. One point has always somewhat unsettled me in the development of sociological theory: while there are theoretical schools that attend to the cultivation and elaboration of theories, a sociological theory seems particularly predestined to be developed from the ground up, collaboratively, as a team effort. If even the design of a tiny technical component requires a larger design team, why should this not be the case in the modeling of a complex society?

Theoretical Notes (2026)

Note 1 – Knowledge as Formal Situation: At the time of writing, a distinction was maintained between knowledge elements and situational elements. Subsequent theoretical development has led to the recognition that knowledge itself constitutes a formal situation – a refinement elaborated in *Serialization as Situation* (Bauer 2026).

Note 2 – The Fundamental Impulse and Human Finitude: The text refers to Schütz's concept of fundamental motives and to the formal impulse as a generalizable action motive. A crucial dimension not yet explicitly developed here is the role of human

finitude as the deepest grounding of the impulse toward unity. Schütz (2003:88;188) named the finiteness of man as a general motive for human action – the principle of the tendency towards unity builds on this insight while extending it to all situations and all living beings, not only to human daily and life plans.

Note 3 – Language and the Formal Situation: The formulation that language is "more than the situation" requires clarification in light of subsequent theoretical development. Language does not transcend the formal situation as such; rather, it operates on the basis of formal situational principles while enabling the construction of higher-order situational contexts through the combination of sentences and narratives. Language is indeed a means of describing situations based on rules of the formal situation.

Note 4 – Self-Referentiality as an Explicit Principle: The self-referential character of situational elements – whereby knowledge elements can themselves constitute situations – is present in the original text but not yet named as an explicit structural principle. Subsequent theoretical development has formalized this as the principle of self-referentiality, which applies to all dimensions of the formal situation.

Note 5 – Reduction of Dimensions: The original text identifies six situational dimensions: time, space, quantity, impulse, knowledge, and exchange. Subsequent theoretical refinement has reduced the core dimensions to three universal ones – space, time, and quantity – while impulse and exchange are reconceived as operational principles rather than independent dimensions. This structural simplification follows the spirit of Occam's razor already invoked in the conclusion.

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List of Figures

Figure 1: Levels of Abstraction 8

Figure 2: Structures of the Lifeworld (after Schütz/Luckmann 2003) 10